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Abstract: Neurolinguistic programming as a method of expressing the student's subjective experience, his thinking, behavior and communicative processes [correct perception of the environment by himself and others, helps to organize effective communication.

Key words: Neurolinguistic, Neuropedagogy, subjective, neuropsychologists.

Recently, scientific directions connecting the issues of education and upbringing processes with the peculiarities of the structure of the student's brain: neuropsychology, neurolinguistics or neuropsycholinguistics, psycholinguistics are developing rapidly. American neuropsychologists called the 90s of the 20th century the "decade of the brain" and emphasized the attention of pedagogues to this topic. According to the instructions given by American neuropsychologists, it is necessary for the teacher to use a wide range of opportunities to involve students in learning activities of different forms and contents, to use different educational methods and methods. At the moment, they call the brain a "parallel processor" that performs several tasks at the same time. can transfer Opinions about the need to use neuroscience data in pedagogy have been put forward by scientists for a long time, but the opportunity to use the achievements of neuropsychology and neurobiology in pedagogical practice in a broad sense appeared at the end of the 20th century. The connection between the structure of the brain and the peculiarities of thought processes has been proven by the scientific research of research scientists from more than twenty countries around the world.

In the 80s of the last century, Y. Lotman conducted research on semiotics and cultural studies based on the successes of neuroscientists. He puts forward the idea of the successive activation of competitive types of consciousness, one of which is detached from the extreme essence, and the other, which serves to reveal the essence in a way that is united with external reality. The foundation of this direction is the scientific researches of psychologists L.S. Vygotsky and A. Leontev in the field of educational psychology and the researches of A. R. Luria, who is considered the founder of neuro-psychology. The product of their scientific research activities is the basis for the creation of children's neuropsychology, in which the general theoretical foundations of normal and abnormal development are expressed. The study of pedagogical processes from the point of view of neurological changes occurring in the human brain, that is, the synergism of neurology and pedagogy, led to the emergence and formation of neuropedagogy as a separate science. Neurobiologists from thirty state institutions on the international scientific project called "Brain and Education" organized by the Center for Educational Research and Innovation (CERI) of the Organization for Economic Cooperation and Development (OeSD). pedagogue, psychologist, sociologist and medical staff conducted scientific research (Brain and Learning). In Russia, the Institute of Cognitive Neuroscience was established under the Academy of Modern Humanities. It serves as a working area for specialists of related profiles in the field of preliminary neuropedagogy. The Institute of Cognitive Neuroscience brings together scientists from Moscow State University, the Institute of the Human Brain of the Russian Academy of

Sciences, the Institute of Psychology, the Scientific Research Institute of Neurocybernetics, Rostov State University.

This direction is directly related to the following pedagogical tasks: application of neuropsychological knowledge in solving problems of learning in the educational process development of neuropsychology of individual differences T.A. conducted a number of studies aimed at explaining the secret. The formation of spirituality in any person takes place in connection with his material and spiritual needs. In turn, the spiritual needs of a person are inextricably linked with his national, religious, ideological and ideological upbringing. At the same time, the material need is related to the simple benefits necessary for people's lifestyle. In this sense, the formation process of human spiritual culture is clearly manifested in the harmony of material and spiritual needs. The formation process of spirituality is based on science, culture, education, moral, aesthetic, political, legal relations and wealth acquired by mankind throughout history. By the last decade of the 20th century, humanity realized that the world can develop fully and sustainably as a single society. "Until our time, human society has not existed as a unified whole," wrote sociologist Anthony Giddens.

A number of socio-ideological situations, globalization and integration processes that occurred in the world at the border of two centuries, i.e. 20th and 21st centuries, divided the world into many poles on the one hand, and on the other hand, connected it to each other. The processes related to globalization and their impact on the world development and the economy, politics and spiritual life of countries make the issues of stability and security more urgent. It is appropriate to analyze the principles of the increasing need for the development of the spiritual culture of the individual in the conditions where the globalization process covers the social development of the present time, socio-economic, political, spiritual and cultural. In fact, this process is considered the most comprehensive and complex social phenomenon, and the main factors of its development and implementation are: formation of international characteristics among different peoples and nations; to constantly enrich the spiritual culture of a person and raise it to a new level of quality; to take into account the interests and needs of the individual; it is necessary to take into account the strong influence of national and religious values on the development of people's spirituality. So, the activity of a person's participation in this process is related to the level of awareness of the existing interests and needs, the increasing need for the development of spiritual culture. It is known that the basis of philological education is expressed in the form of symbols, symbols, words, images, and serves the development of a person's intellect, outlook and thinking. Of course, a person's personal attitude to things and events plays an important role in this process. As stated by M. Kuronov, "For the purposes of mutual conversation, education, propaganda, knowingly or unknowingly, a person spreads his relations through his thoughts. As a result, the attitude of one person can become the attitude of hundreds of people to this or that thing or event. Because a person often tries to convince the interlocutor next to something, to change his behavior, to change his opinion to his opinion, to change his wishes to the wishes of many, to change his beliefs to the beliefs of many ". With one word, he tries to lead the interlocutor to his goals, to convince and convince him of his point of view. In terms of modern science, it uses neurolinguistic programming technologies. Today, there is a special need to apply neurolinguistic programming technology in philological education.

Neurolinguistic programming as a way of expressing the student's subjective experience, his thinking, behavior and communicative processes [correct perception of the environment by

himself and others, helps to organize effective communication. Neurolinguistic programming makes it possible to use it successfully based on the analysis of the student's behavioral strategy. Neurolinguistic programming is considered a humanitarian technology of education, and its main task is to form effective communication techniques in order to achieve guaranteed results in the development of spiritual culture in students, and activities aimed at consciously changing the behavior of oneself and the people around. consists of preparation. The essence of the "neuro-linguistic programming" technology was briefly and clearly expressed in M. Kuronov's book "The Truth We Understand" as follows: "Persuasion is an idea that is conveyed to one person by another person (or means) by creating exciting moments or by making everyone recognize the method of absorption depending on the sources. Persuasion is the ultimate form of persuasion. The same process takes place in self-persuasion. However, it is not an external factor, but a person's own feelings that take part in introducing thoughts and ideas." There are three main elements of Neuro-Linguistic Programming:

- "neuro" - the connection of the nervous system between the brain and the body;
- "linguistics" - interaction through words and language;
- "programming" means systematizing thoughts and actions that are repeated in a sequence.

So, controlling a person's thoughts and behavior through language and words is the main essence of neurolinguistic programming. Various methods and techniques of neurolinguistic programming can be used in philological education. Here are some of these neurolinguistic programming techniques:

Adaptation and management. This technique forms the basis of linguistic programming, and in order to successfully influence the student's moral behavior, it is important to adapt to his actions (state, mood, gaze, posture, position of hands and feet). Adapting to the rhythm of breathing is effective in providing a clearly focused effect on the student. To do this, it is necessary to observe the student's breathing, to be silent while breathing, on the contrary, to address him when he breathes out. As a result, in the subconscious state of the student, the words that are said to him leave an impression as if they were being said by him. Let's say a student is angry about a reprimand. In this case, the teacher is required to enter the physiological state as if he were angry, that is, to adapt to the situation of the student. It is necessary to continue the conversation at this pace, gradually the teacher should moderate his mental state. The student, in turn, adapts to the calm state of the teacher and calmly approaches the situation. It is known that the brains of students, like all people, are designed to work with constant and unchanging information. Being prevented from increasing the behavior one wants, creates a trance state in them and allows to effectively influence their behavior. In this case, it is especially appropriate to use pedagogical situations focused on involvement, cooperation, tension and elimination. In the situation of involvement, students are taught to understand that they are directly related to the current problems of our time, to feel the need to feel responsibility for all the events that are happening in the world. an idea is formed about the means of achieving the goal. In the situation of the experience, the teacher confronts the students with the reality related to some kind of spiritual depravity.

This situation occurs at the emotional, logical, and operational levels (determining one's attitude and determining the direction of one's behavior in this situation). The situation of tension is aimed at actively holding serious spiritual and moral feelings of a person for a long period of time, and this situation forces students to show moral stability. The more long-term and intense the activity, the higher the stability of moral manifestations required of the student. Later, there is

a need for manifestations in the situation of eliminating spiritual and moral stereotypes. Students expect the teacher to get angry, express traditional opinions, and give a serious lecture, but in order to eliminate stereotypes in students, in this situation, they need to be polite in a way they did not expect, introduce non-standard situations, give a lecture. It is necessary to use laughter in the process.

Fight against destructive rumors. This technique is part of preventive measures and allows students to be protected from informational attacks against our national spiritual heritage, national values, and historical figures. For this purpose, the teacher should study, systematize, and neutralize the rumors that have entered the minds and hearts of the students and in order to destroy their faith in the reforms. According to M. Kuronov, two ways appear in front of the teacher-coach in the campaign against rumors:

1) to remain silent (which means inaction in relation to the spread rumor or encouraging it);

2) disclosure (although this may also cause further spread of destructive rumors that are being exposed!). Continuing his opinion, the scientist explains that the solution to this in the history of propaganda is not to directly expose the rumor, but to dispel it with the help of facts. Therefore, if there are rumors of moral threat among students, the teacher should effectively use training sessions, videos and visual aids that eliminate its destructive effect.

Indifference - prevention of lack of will. This technique is aimed at finding new ideas and desires, a sense of creativity in the minds of students, and serves to eliminate hesitation and weakness of will energy. For this, the teacher should first of all make the students believe in their own strength and capabilities. Trust is not created by itself. For this purpose, it is desirable that the ideas given to the students should be repeatedly broadcasted in connection with the practice, presented in a visual, figurative way, and inculcated based on tested examples. Confidence, in turn, gives rise to desire and intention and gives energy to the will, the source of action. Willful, active, mediocre, apathetic, apathetic learners are among the students. But in order to make them all move together, it is necessary to propose a goal and idea that everyone can quickly and easily understand, and to convince them that it is important.

Exercise "Freedom of choice in acquiring knowledge". On the basis of this technique, students will have the opportunity to understand what they want to learn, the reasons that motivate them, and the consequences of the situations in which they want to study and do not want to. The exercise helps students to make good use of internal contradictions to be conscious and responsible towards learning. For this, the teacher offers the students to make a list of freedom of choice in acquiring knowledge. At first, the teacher asks the students to compile a set of life experiences of people they know in their notebooks. Then he explains that they should exchange notebooks from time to time, each time writing one of their life experiences based on examples.

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